

Metamorphic records of partial subduction and continental collision in and around the parautochthon of the NW Iberian Massif

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The parautochthonous domains of the Variscan Orogen represent paleogeographic and geodynamic intermediate pieces of a large thrust pile that separates the autochthon from an upper set of allochthonous terranes and ophiolites representing a suture zone. In contrast to the early subduction-related HP metamorphism that affected some of the allochthonous units, the parautochthonous and autochthonous domains are commonly thought to have not been involved in the continental subduction process, their imprints of intermediate to LP metamorphism being related to subsequent collisional tectonics. New data from the NW of the Iberian Massif (Fig. 1a), point to a more complex scenario in which at least part of the parautochthonous section experienced HP/L-IT conditions before the onset of Barrovian metamorphism. Moreover, some sections of the autochthon immediately beneath the parautochthonous nappes also preserve evidences for an initial P/T gradient higher than classical Barrovian.

The Upper Parautochthonous nappe beneath the allochthonous complexes of Cabo Ortegal and Órdenes is mostly formed by pelitic and semipelitic schists, which may contain albite porphyroblasts trapping tiny aligned inclusions of Qz, Tur, Rt, Ilm and rare white mica (WM). These minerals define an internal schistosity (S_i) that can vary from previous to equivalent to the main external schistosity (S_e). Both, WM from S_i and matrix micas crenulated by S_e , show high silica contents and mineral chemistry compatible with HP/L-IT metamorphic conditions. Combined Massonne and Schreyer (1987) Si-in-phengite geobarometer and PI-Ms geothermometer (Green and Usdansky, 1986) suggest P_{min} conditions = 11-14 kbar and $T = 450-500$ °C for the early metamorphic recrystallization of these rocks (1, 2 in Fig. 1b). No HP/L-IT relics have been found in the rest of the Upper Parautochthonous nappes or in the Lower Parautochthon.

On the contrary, THERMOCALC (Powell and Holland, 1988) average P-T estimations of the Barrovian assemblage Grt + Bt + Pl + Ms + AIS + Rt + Ilm on pelitic schists from the Lower Parautochthonous nappe affected by the extensional Arnoia Detachment (Celanova Dome), yield prograde conditions around 7.5 Kbar and 600-700 °C (fields 3c-Grt center, 3r-Grt rim in Fig. 1b; 4c-Grt center, 4r-Grt rim for the retrograde evolution of the detachment), which are lower in P and considerably higher in T than the former HP/L-IT conditions.

In the autochthons of the Sanabria region, Ky-bearing slates and veins also show low-T assemblages with high-silica WM, Chl, Rt, Il and Ap (Bt- and Pl-free). The Massonne and Schreyer (1987) barometer yields P_{min} of 9.0 kbar for temperatures that can not be too much higher than the pyrophyllite = Ky + Qz + H₂O reaction, proceeding at 425-450 °C (field 5 in Fig. 1b). On the other hand, THERMOCALC average P-T analyses on Early Ordovician schists from the Villadepera Antiform displaying Grt + Bt + Pl + Ms + AIS + Rt + Ilm, give conditions near 11-12 kbar and 700-725 °C (6c-Grt center, 6r-Grt rim, Fig. 1b). Such conditions are markedly higher in T than those above of the Ky-bearing rocks, and match those registered by correlative rocks from central Iberia (paths A and B in Fig. 1b).

References

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